

IMPACT OF COVID 19 AND LOCKDOWN ON INDIAN ECONOMY: SOME POLICIES

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Abstract:

COVID 19 is an infectious disease caused by corona virus. Taking its birth in the Wuhan city in China during December 2019 this virus spreads all through the world including India within a short span of time. In a state of no vaccine or no medicine, the government of India along with other parts of the world, called on the nationwide lockdown, to cope up the situation. The present paper focuses the impact of lockdown on the health of industry, tourism, growth of GDP and the migrant labours in India. It is found that, the world's biggest (69 days) nationwide lockdown adversely affected all the sectors of economy triggering a global economic crisis. The production system is collapsed. The contraction in IIP becomes 57.6% (April, 2020). Large number of private sector employee and labours especially migrant one become jobless. The collection of revenue turns into the lowest amount and so the sum of GDP. The social and economic life of the nation becomes standstill thereby upsetting the communities as a whole.

Key Words: Lockdown, economy, Manufacturing, GDP, Migrant workers

Introduction:

COVID 19 is an infectious disease having severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). It is caused by the respiratory pathogen: corona virus. It is identified first in the Wuhan city in China in December 2019 and spreads rapidly all through the world within a short span of time as a Global pandemic. India recorded its first confirmed case of COVID 19 on 30th January, 2020 in Kerala. In the situation of no vaccine or medicine, the only way to combat with the disease is to quarantine the people at home (Zhu W et al 2019). For this, India, along with the other countries of the world walks on the way of lockdown. The government declared here a long-term nationwide lockdown from 24th March to 30th May followed by sixth phase unlock periods.

The situation of lockdown prohibited the people from stepping out of their homes. All the means of transport is suspended for public uses. At most all the sectors of economy are about to shut, which affects the consumption of both essential and discretionary items. The process of production is hindered by the shortage of raw materials (FICCI, 2020). The growth of index of industrial production becomes the least. Same trend is noticed in manufacturing sector, in mining sector, in service sector, in agriculture and so on. As a result of the sudden closure of the national and state boarder and collapse of the transportation system, there is a complete crumple of the domestic and global supply chains with no movement of raw materials and finished products. Large numbers of workers become jobless. Declining in income, affect the private spending negatively and so the demand for goods and services. All this causes the financial instability of the economy (UNCTAD, 2020). The international monetary fund has uttered that, the possibility of global recession is very high in the developing countries including India where poverty level is still high (Baldwin R. et al). According to their estimate, as a result of the COVID 19 pandemic, the global economy is expected to contract by -4.9% growth in 2020 which is much inferior than during 2008-2009 financial crisis. During April 2020, former chief, RBI, Dr. Raghuram Rajan, said that, the COVID 19 pandemic is the greatest emergency since independence" (Ghosh 2020).

In this light, the present paper is an attempt to analyse the impact of COVID 19 pandemic and nationwide lockdown on different sectors of Indian economy especially on industry and MSME (Micro, small and medium Enterprises), tourism, GDP generation and migrant labours and to suggest appropriate theoretical and managerial implications.

Data Base and Methodology:

The present study is based on the secondary information which is collected from various official websites, newspaper, reports of different rating agencies and World Bank, WHO COVID 19 data base and many articles published in national and international journals. Data regarding industrial production and GDP has been collected from the Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation (MoSPI) and National Statistical Organization (NSO), Govt. of India. The website of the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy Pvt. Ltd is used to collect data regarding the status of unemployment. Data regarding up to date number of COVID positive patient and death have been collected from publicly available portal of WHO COVID 19 data base and the Ministry of Home and Family Welfare, Govt. of India.

The methodology used for this study is quantitative as well as qualitative. The method of analysis applied here includes a combination of thematic mapping followed by statistical analysis. Smart art graphic has been used to show the impact of lockdown to important economic sectors. Growth rate of IIP, GDP and the

status of unemployment of labour have been shown with the help of line graph made on the basis of collected and compiled data. Bargraph has also been prepared to show the comparative growth rate of IIP and quarterly growth of GDP.

Economic Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic in India:

Figure 1: Impact of COVID-19 and lockdown in Indian economy.

India is one of the worst affected (COVID 19) countries of the world and so it experiences a prolonged economic decelerate during the pandemic. The long term nationwide lock down has adversely impacted all the sectors of economy of the country, jeopardizing the lively hood of the Indian. Both the supply and the demand side are highly shocked. Manufacturing, trade, service, import, export; all the sectors are highly affected. According to Adar Poonawalla, the CEO of the Serum Institute of India, "the economic risk of the outbreak is exponentially greater than its health risks"¹. Here in the following sections, impact of lockdown on selected important sectors of Indian economy is discussed.

Impact on Industry:

In today’s India, industrial sectors especially manufacturing, mining, electricity and MSME play a vital role in generating revenue (GDP, 30%) and employment (26%) in the country. COVID 19 pandemic made a massive shock to all the industrial establishments since the end of March 2020. It attacks this sector by

- Disrupting the production process.
- Shortening the inputs for production.
- Making the crisis of labor forces.

This has had a great impact on the country’s economy during and after the period of lockdown. The demand and supply side of this sector is stunned due to the collapse of the transportation system and boarder closure. As per the data provided by the Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, Govt of India (MoSPI), it is found that, the index of industrial production (IIP) started to decline from the beginning of 2020 and becomes the highest in April. The average year-on-year contraction in this sector was 57.6% to 54.0 in this month as compared to 16.7% contraction during March 2020. It is the maximum contraction in this sector for a period of last three decades. The contraction was 64.3% on-year to 42.1 in manufacturing sector, 27.4% on-year to 78.7 in mining sector and 22.6% on-year to 125.5 in electricity generation. In the months of May, June, July and August the tempo of contraction of IIP were 34.7%, 16.6%, 10.4%, and 8.6% respectively as compared to the same period in the last year. Parallel to this, the contraction is noticed also in case of use based goods. The data shows that, the contraction in case of primary goods output was 26.6%, capital goods output was 92%, intermediate goods output was 66.4% and infrastructure and construction goods output was 83.9% in this month. In the April-July period of 2020-21 FY, the contraction rate becomes 29.2% as compared to 3.5% growth in the corresponding period of the previous year.

Table 1: Growth of the Index of Industrial Production (Base: 2011-12=100)

Year	Months	Situation	Growth of IIP		% Growth of IIP	
			2020	2019	2020	2019
2000	Jan	Normal	137.4	134.4	+2.2	+1.6
2000	Feb	Normal	134.2	127.6	+5.2	+0.2
2000	Mar	Lockdown starts on 24.3.20	117.2	144.1	-16.7	2.7

¹ The Economic Times, 20 March 2020, Retrieved on 21.03.2020

2000	Apr	Lockdown	54.0	126.5	-57.6	3.2
2000	May	Lockdown	90.2	135.4	-34.7	4.5
2000	Jun	Unlock Phase-1	107.9	129.3	-16.6	1.3
2000	Jul	Unlock Phase-2	118.1	131.8	-10.4	4.9
2000	Aug	Unlock Phase-3	116.9	126.2	-7.4	-1.4
2000	Sep	Unlock Phase-4	123.5	122.9	+0.5	-4.6
2000	Oct	Unlock Phase-5	128.5	124.0	+3.6	-6.6

Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation (MoSPI).

Figure 2: Comparative growth (%) and General of IIP in some selected months in 2019 and 2020.

Thereafter in the month of September, the growth rate enters in positive zone. A slide growth (0.5%) is noticed in the index of industrial production (IIP) in this month. In the sectors like mining, manufacturing and electricity the corresponding growth increase to 1.4%, -0.2% and 4.9% respectively.

Point to note that, there is a continuous declining trend of IIP growth (general & sectoral) since 2016-17. Highest decline is noticed in the manufacturing sector.

Table 2: General and Sectorial growth of IIP (%) since 2016-17 (Base: 2011-12=100)

Groups	Weight (%)	Growth of IPP (%)					
		Annual				Monthly	
		2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	Sept 2020	Oct 2020
Mining	14.373	5.3	2.3	2.9	1.6	1.4	-1.5
Manufacturing	77.633	5.4	4.6	3.9	-1.4	-0.2	3.5
Electricity	7.994	5.8	5.4	5.2	1.0	4.9	11.2
General Index	100.00	4.6	4.4	3.8	-0.8	0.5	3.6

Source: National Statistical Organization (NSO).

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise (MSME) is also an important sector in Indian economy. It is engaged primarily in the production, manufacturing, processing or preservation of goods and commodities. As per the Annual Reports of the Govt. of India (2018-19), there are more than 6 crores of MSME in the country which play a key role in socioeconomic development of the country by earning foreign exchange and by generating employment. In India, MSME contributes around 45% of the manufacturing output, about 40% of the country's export and about 8% of the country's GDP (Gross Domestic Product). It is the second largest employment generator (after agriculture) employing more than 114 million people².

During nationwide lockdown this sector faces the worsening situation in importing raw materials, producing goods and exporting the finished products. So most of these remained shut and so the production. These entire facade a havoc loss. Generally they have loan obligations and monthly EMI (equated monthly installment) to pay. They face a critical situation regarding the payment of their employees and EMIs.

Impact on Tourism Industry:

India, because of its uniqueness in tradition, culture and unparalleled hospitality, it has the largest market in tourism industry in south East Asia. This country is a key destination of many international tourists which generates employment opportunity for the local people and earns huge foreign exchanges (Ahmed & Krohn, 1992). It is important also in the sense that, it benefits many other sectors like lodging, catering, transportation, retail, entertainment, etc contributing to economic growth and development. Earning INR 194 billion of revenues in 2018, this sector contributes 9.2% of the country's GDP (WTTC, 2018, Jagan Mohan, 2020). In 2019 more than 10.8 million of foreign travelers travel India with a foreign exchange earning of USD 268.9 billion (FICCI, 2020). It accounts about 87.5 million jobs (12.75 % of the country's total).

COVID 19 and associated lockdown has had a great impact on the health of global tourism including India (Gössling et al 2020). During nationwide lockdown India completely closes its boarder and cancelled all

² Central Statistics Office, (CSO), Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Govt. of India

flights including entertainment and pilgrimages. Along with this several measures like social distancing, stay at and work from home, self or mandatory-quarantine, curbs on crowding, etc are implemented which create great shock in tourism industry in this country. (Gretzel et al., 2020; Sigala, 2020). It is estimated that, due to the lockdown there is a fall of 66.4% overseas tourist's arrivals in India in March 2020 as compared to the last year making a fall of 66.32% foreign exchange earnings for the country.(TAN, 2020, Statista, 2020).According to the calculation of FICCI there will be about 40 million direct and indirect job losses in India, with an annual loss in revenue of around USD 17 billion (FICCI, 2020; Scroll, 2020).

Impact on GDP Growth:

GDP or gross domestic product is a very important indicator of the economic health of a country. Being the fastest growing economy, India witnessed an upward trend in GDP growth rate since 2012 with some fluctuations during 2016 and 20017. Lockdown has downturned the graph by crashing the supply side of the economy like manufacturing, mining, electricity generation and services like transportation, distribution of goods, trade etc.

According to the estimates of the World Bank, the growth of GDP in India will downgrade in the lowest figures (1.5% to 2.8%) for the fiscal year 2020-21 in the three decades since India's economic liberalization in 1990s (The Hindu News). The study made by the State Bank of India, shows that, there will be a contraction of over 40% in the India's GDP during the FY 2020-21³. The Asian development Bank estimated that, Indian GDP growth for the FY 2020-21 will slip to 4.8% (Press Trust of India). The research conducted by MotilalVora suggests that, a single day complete lockdown could shave off 14-19 basis points from the annual growth. (Oswal, 2020). The IEA has estimated that, fall of GDP will be at the rate of 2%/month of lockdown. (IEA 2020). The cumulative shutdown cost in India may be around 120 billion US dollars which is equal to 4% of total GDP. (Barclays, 2020).

In reality it is found that, the GDP growth rate of this country has fallen from 8.2% in January-March 2018 to 3.1% in January-March 2020⁴, which is still falling. It becomes negative during the first quarter of 2020-21 due to decline of crucial parameters like manufacturing, mining, construction, trade and tourism industry. In the second quarter (July-September) of this FY (Fiscal Year) the GDP is contracted by 7.5% from the same quarter of the last year, following an unprecedented year-on-year decline of 23.9% in the April-June quarter. It is the lowest in the economic history of the country (Paliwal 2020). During 2019-20 FY the fiscal deficit of this country becomes 3.8% against the expected target of 3.3% which is still rising. The quarterly growth of GDP also shows a constant decrease since 4th quarter of 2018-19.

Table 3: India's GDP growth rate since FY 2015-16

FY	GDP growth rate (%)	% increase
2015-16	8.0	-
2016-17	8.3	(+0.3%)
2017-18	6.6	(-1.4%)
2018-19	6.1	(-0.5%)
2019-20	4.2	(-1.9% est.)
2020-21	-5.0	(-9.2% est.)

Source: The Indian Express. Retrieved 30 May 2020.

Figure 3: Growth rate of GDP over the years

Source- Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, GOI

³Economy may contract by over 40% in q1, SBI research, The Economic Times, 27 May, 2020, Retrieved on 28.5.20

⁴"Infographic: India's GDP Collapses In Face of Pandemic". StatistaInfographics. Retrieved 4 September 2020.

During that period, the growth was 5.8%. With time it starts to decline and becomes the least (-23.9%) in the 1st quarter of 2020-21 due to the direct impact of COVID 19 and country wide lockdown (Table-4, fig-4). In this period (April), Indian exports are decreased by -36.65% as compared to the same period of the previous year were as the import is chopped down by -47.36% in the same month⁵.

Migrant Workers:

Unemployment is a great problem in India. This generates thousands and thousands of surplus labour forces in different states of the country. As a result they have to migrate elsewhere in search of employment and to some extent for better wage. Lion’s share of India’s surplus labors move from UP and Bihar to Punjab, Haryana, Maharashtra and Gujarat, from West Bengal, Orissa and North East to Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh and Kerala, from Rajasthan and MP to Gujarat and Maharashtra and so on. These workers are employed mainly in construction sector (about 40 mln), domestic work (about 20 mln), textile sector (about 11 mln), in brick making work (about 10 mln), agriculture, mining, transportation and so on⁶.

During nationwide lockdown, all the sectors of economy in India is about to shut except essential services. As a result, millions of labours and factory workers become jobless and so are to deal with the loss of income and food shortage (Masih 2020, Singh 2020). In this period, about half of the Indian households have reported an income drop as compared the previous year (CMIE). More than 14 crores workers have lost their jobs across the nation in the lockdown. The graph suddenly attain in the peak (24.95%) during the initial phase of the lockdown.

Table 4: Unemployment situation in India during COVID 19 pandemic

Year	Months	Rate of unemployment (%)		
		India	Urban	Rural
2019	December	7.6	9.02	6.93
2020	January	7.22	9.70	6.06
2020	February	7.76	8.65	7.34
2020	March	8.75	9.41	8.44
2020	April	23.52	24.95	22.89
2020	May	21.73	23.14	21.14
2020	June	10.18	11.68	9.49
2020	July	7.40	9.37	6.51
2020	August	8.35	9.83	7.65

Source; Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy Pvt. Ltd

Figure 4: Rate of unemployment in India during pandemic

From a survey conducted by Jan Saahas from March 27 to march 29, it is found that, out of 3195 migrant workers across the northern-central India, 80% of them feared about the shortage of food and joblessness during the lock down period, 94% of them get below minimum wage, 49% of them get no ration inspite of having their Adhar card and bank account in most cases with them. It was difficult enough for most of them to avail the benefit of the relief package and free ration declared by the central government. They are trapped in sealed cities with no jobs, no income and so are at a great risk of falling deeper into. This situation of uncertainty, starvation and eagerness to reach their home triggered the movement of millions of migrant labours to their families.

⁵ “India’s Foreign Trade: April 2020” pib.gov.in. Ministry of Commerce and Industry 15 May 2020. Retrieved 15 June 2020.

⁶IIPS (2001), Major net migration flows. Indian Institute of Population Sciences.

But as the transportation system is collapsed totally, thousands of migrant workers are seen walking or bicycling hundreds of kilometers toward their homes (Jaiswal 2020). Many of them become arrested for the violation of lockdown or die in hungry or by accidents (Babu et al 2020, Elsa et al 2020). To get rid of the problem, some state governments arrange buses for their return (Jha, S 2020). Lastly on May 1, the central government arranges trains (Shramik Special) to move the migrant workers to their villages (Bhargava 2020).

Conclusion and Policy Proposals:

The unprecedented situation of corona virus and associated COVID 19 pandemic has caused a great crisis to Indians economy. Its outbreak starts in such a time in this country when its economy is facing slowdown. The recession gets a momentum during this period. All the sectors of economy are highly affected due to supply shock, demand shock and the market shock. As a result, contraction in growth in all its sectors (manufacturing 64%, industrial sector 57%. capital goods 92% in April 2020) turns into sky touching. Trade and commerce sectors are positioned at about 50% narrowing. Same trend is noticed in case of MSMEs, tourism, transportation, employment etc. MSMEs turn into the worstly affected sector. The quarterly growth of GDP becomes -23.9% in the first quarter of 2020-21 FY. Millions of country's workers become jobless.

The economic disaster created in India due to this world's biggest lockdown is dual in nature. It is a combination of health crisis and economic crisis. So the government will have to cope up the situation by providing health related infrastructure like new hospitals with sufficient number of beds, doctors and nursing staff, ventilators, medicines, masks, sanitizers, PPE, gloves etc to enrich the health sectors and by the introduction of fiscal and monetary stimulus packages in the economic sectors in order to boost up the financial system and to protect the lives and livelihood of the country.

It is worth mentioning that, the Reserve Bank of India already has declared several monetary policy measures to fight against with the calamity. Relief package of more than INR (Indian national rupee) 20 lakhs crores has been provided in different phases to inject lifeblood to different sectors of economy including the moratorium on payment of installments on existing term loans of MSMEs, incentives to the worst affected unorganized sectors, direct cash transfer to ensure food security of weaker section and marginalized communities, job creation for the migrant workers etc.

But it is not sufficient for the streamlining of a bigger sized economy like India. So the government should take the initiatives in restructuring the country's economy especially in rural areas by developing infrastructural facilities. According to the availability of local resources, the government may focus on the development of the small scale production centers or service centers in the rural areas, inspite of making larger corporation. It will breed up the agro based industries, better access to market for farmers, generate job opportunities for the rural population and improve the purchase power of the villagers. It will also boost up the MSME sectors. The govt. also ensures the provision of working capital at low interest rates to start-ups and small and medium industries to tide over the recession.

Priority also to be given in the core sectors of the country like agriculture, industry, healthcare etc. It may trigger of the growth of the nation. Structural reforms are needed to flourish the sectors like agriculture and industry rather than the temporary awareness. Attention must be given to the development of infrastructure for quality education. Children are totally deprived of the learning from the first day of the lockdown although a section of them got the facility of distance learning.

For this, the government must needs to arrive at a key plan. A best suited forecasting model should be developed which can help in operational decision making. The policy makers and the stakeholders must think about the existing resources more proficient and efficiently inspite of adding new more resources. All these can make a V shaped expansion of countries economy which is very essential in post pandemic period to achieve the target of 5 trillion in coming 2024-25 (Sharma, E 2020).

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Not Applicable.

Abbreviations:

- MSME = Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.
- CEO = Chief Executive Officer
- GDP = Gross Domestic Product
- MoSPI = Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, Govt of India
- IIP = Index of Industrial Production
- EMI = Equated monthly installment
- FY = Fiscal Year
- INR = Indian Rupee

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